

ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF ASSETS DIVERSIFICATION IN THE BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT BANK OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the internal factors, structure of assets and liabilities, bank innovations, material and technical base and the state of asset diversification of the joint-stock commercial bank “Business Development Bank”.

Key words: agriculture, financial resource, authorized capital, foreign currency, branch, problem assets, investment.

The preservation of the priority of credit investments in the volume of assets at the moment requires the solution of the problem of proportionality in terms of the duration of the collection of assets and liabilities.

The provision of resources at the expense of funds attracted by the conditions until a certain part of the loan investment is “requisitioned” can make the current liquidity management process difficult.

Optimizing the structure of assets and liabilities, increasing the efficiency of work in the management of risks arising from asset operations, including loans, remain relevant.

The main credit investments of the JSCB “Business Development Bank” were analyzed by sectors of the economy: industry, agriculture, transport and communications, construction, trade and public catering, material and technical support, housing and communal services, for individuals: commercial loans, individual entrepreneurs and others, loans allocated: short, long, cotton and grain loans, commercial loans, including consumer loans, mortgage loans, loans allocated for investment, repaid: short, long, cotton and grain loans, commercial loans. The amount of credit investments by industry as of January 1, 2017 amounted to 843 billion soums (Table 1).

Table 1

Analysis of credit investments placed by JSCB “Business Development Bank” by sectors and their repayment

N	Main indicators	2017	2018	2019	2020	2023
5	Credit investments by economic sectors					
-	Industry	843	701	670	3 514	7 593
-	Agriculture	1 176	1 637	2 929	5 739	15 125
-	Transport and communications	61	41	33	105	86
-	Construction	37	193	28	207	135
-	Trade and catering	42	22	85	188	139
-	Material and technical support	105	28	1 806	1 403	732
-	Housing and communal services	0	0	47	192	263
-	Individuals	352	546	1 409	3 157	5 119
	<i>-commercial loans</i>	327	262	765	1 389	1 028
	<i>-each family is an entrepreneur</i>	25	284	645	1 768	4 091
-	Others	387	205	1 743	1 360	4 094
	TOTAL	3 003	3 373	8 750	15 866	32 258
6	Loans allocated	4 717	5 693	13 348	19 176	29 409
-	short	2 217	2 054	4 093	7 549	11 296
-	long	2 500	3 639	9 255	11 626	18 113
-	cotton and grain loans	2 357	3 191	6 362	8 534	9 815
-	commercial loans	2 360	2 502	6 986	10 642	19 595
	<i>including</i>					
	- consumer loans	43	40	748	742	2 437
	- mortgage loans	46	8	10	82	168
	- investment loans	831	1 034	2 296	4 821	9 849
7	Repaid		5 322	7 971	12 060	17 794
-	short		1 787	2 607	6 774	6 991
-	long		3 535	5 364	5 287	10 803
-	cotton and grain loans		3 172	4 972	6 468	6 916
-	commercial loans		2 150	2 999	5 592	10 878

The problem loans available at the Business Development Bank (number of clients: 162,398) were analyzed and amounted to: 10.3 billion soums in 2017, 30.3 billion soums in 2018, 33.9 billion soums in 2019, 29.0 billion soums in 2020, 137.9 billion soums in 2021, 724.4 billion soums in 2022, 1,190.5 billion soums in January 2023, and 1,869.1 billion soums in May 2023. If we compare over the years,

it increased by 20 billion soums in 2017-2018, by 1 billion soums in 2018-2019, by 4.9 billion soums in 2019-2020, by 108.9 billion soums in 2020-2021, by 586.5 billion soums in 2021-2022, and by 466.1 billion soums in 2022-2023. If we take problem loans as a whole, they amounted to 679 billion soums as of 01.01.2023 and 15.7% in interest. As of 01.01.2022, they amounted to 1,145 billion soums and 25.8% in interest (Table 2).

Table 2

Analysis of problem assets of JSCB “Business Development Bank”

N	Key indicators	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	01.05.2023
1	Problem assets								
1.1	Problem loans (number of clients 162,398)	10,3	30,3	33,9	29,0	137,9	724,4	1 190,5	1 869,1
	- Overdue loans (158,362)	5,3	28,5	31,5	23,6	84,1	675,6	1 140,0	1 754,0
	- Loans in litigation (4,036)	4,9	1,8	2,5	5,5	47,9	48,8	50,5	112,4
	Extended loans (35,273 clients)	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,9	4,9	3,3	2,6
	Non-performing loans - NPL (74,449)	6,3	31,5	178,1	95	308	1 495,1	1 685,3	1 888,2
	- Unsatisfactory	1,3	15,3	16,7	3	76	146,9	888,4	526,4
	- Doubtful	1,4	7,5	8,0	1	65	263,7	422,0	462,3
	- Hopeless	3,6	8,7	153,4	92	167	1 084,4	374,9	899,6
	Share of problem loans in total investment	0%	0,4%	2,0%	0,6%	1,2%	4,6%	3,8%	3,8%
	Reserve created for loans	7,1	20,5	125,5	94	266	594	813	1 262
1.2	Balance of loan “Cotton 2018-2019”		151,3	88,8	39,2	35,7	0,0	0,0	0,0
	of which farms were liquidated		12,5	68,8	12,3	12,3	0,0	0,0	0,0
1.3	Accrued interest (16,300)	8,1	8,4	46,9	44,2	215,2	515,0	1 072,2	1 841,0
	of which overdue interest (16,377)	0,6	0,3	3,0	3,0	15,8	53,8	123,1	195,0
1.4	Settlement brokerage commission (16,400)	2,8	9,4	4,4	7,2	11,2	68,6	249,8	407,1
1.5	Other private property of the bank (16,700)	1,0	0,0	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
1.6	Overdue interest (91,500)	27,4	23,3	29,2	39,8	85,7	114,7	512,6	578,6
1.7	Credit balance of corporate clients	815,7	591,1	1 932,2	1 760,7	1 161,4	989,1	16 528,0	19 423,0
1.8	Clusters cotton textiles	344,7	216,0	70,4	4,2	1,5	1,3	15 369,7	18 622,8
1.9	JSC “Uzdonmahsulotlari”	354,1	281,2	285,3	369,7	220,1	179,0	472,8	189,3
1.10	JSC “Uzagrokimiyohimoya”	99,3	93,4	285,5	209,2	266,3	266,1	256,4	250,8
	- revolving loans	0,0	49,9	54,7	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
1.11	JSC “Uzagroservis”	17,6	0,6	1 291,0	1 177,5	673,5	542,7	429,2	360,1

Overdue debt (158,362): in 2017 - 5.3 billion soums, in 2018 - 28.5 billion soums, in 2019 - 31.5 billion soums, in 2020 - 23.6 billion soums, in 2021 - 84.1 billion soums, in 2022 - 675.6 billion soums, in 2023 - 1754.0 billion soums. If we consider the difference by years, then in 2017-2018 it was 23.2 billion soums, in 2018-2019 it increased by 3 billion soums, in 2019-2020 it decreased by 7.9 billion soums, in 2020-2021 it reached 60.5 billion soums, in 2021-2022 it reached 591.5 billion soums, and in 2022-2023 it reached 614 billion soums. These figures are 614 billion soums and 15.4% per annum in 2023.

Conclusion.

It should be noted that our country has a number of pressing problems in the management of assets of commercial banks. One of these pressing problems is the large amount of overdue debt on loans issued by commercial banks. The deepening of the problem of overdue debt on loans led to the fact that this issue was reflected in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PR-3270 dated September 12, 2017 “On measures to further develop and increase the stability of the banking system of the Republic”.

There is also the problem of non-return of foreign currency loans issued by commercial banks to the real sector of the economy. Therefore, the existence of problems associated with improving the management of assets of commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the need to solve them was determined as the main objective of this article.

Used literature:

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